

Efficient Large Numbers Karatsuba-Ofman Multiplier Designs for Embedded Systems

M.Machhout, M.Zeghid, W.El hadj youssef, B.Bouallegue, A.Baganne, and R.Tourki

Abstract—Long number multiplications ($n \geq 128$ -bit) are a primitive in most cryptosystems. They can be performed better by using Karatsuba-Ofman technique. This algorithm is easy to parallelize on workstation network and on distributed memory, and it's known as the practical method of choice. Multiplying long numbers using Karatsuba-Ofman algorithm is fast but is highly recursive. In this paper, we propose different designs of implementing Karatsuba-Ofman multiplier. A mixture of sequential and combinational system design techniques involving pipelining is applied to our proposed designs. Multiplying large numbers can be adapted flexibly to time, area and power criteria. Computationally and occupation constrained in embedded systems such as: smart cards, mobile phones..., multiplication of finite field elements can be achieved more efficiently. The proposed designs are compared to other existing techniques. Mathematical models (Area (n), Delay (n)) of our proposed designs are also elaborated and evaluated on different FPGAs devices.

Keywords—finite field, Karatsuba-Ofman, long numbers, multiplication, mathematical model, recursivity.

I. INTRODUCTION

FINITE field multiplication in $GF(2^n)$ is one of the most important operations in cryptographic protocols (RSA, Diffie-Hellman key exchange, DSS, ECC ...) [1, 8, 21]. That means the optimization on multiplication is critical for overall performance of cryptographic implementations. It is very costly in terms of Area and Delay performances. A lot of researches have been performed in designing performant multipliers (low Area occupation and high-speed computation). Several designs have been reported for multiplication on fields of characteristic two [16]. Efficient bit-parallel multipliers for both canonical and normal basis representation as well as hybrid multiplication have been proposed in literature [15]. All these algorithms exhibit a

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Manuscript received March 11, 2008.

space complexity of $O(n^2)$. However, there are some asymptotically faster methods for finite field multiplications, such as the Recursive Karatsuba-Ofman Algorithm [18]. Published in 1962, it was the first algorithm to accomplish polynomial multiplication in $O(n^{1.58})$ operations [20]. The Karatsuba-Ofman Algorithm (KOA) can successfully be applied to polynomial multiplication step. The fundamental Karatsuba-Ofman multiplication (KM) for polynomial in $GF(2^n)$ is based on the idea of divide-and-conquer, since the operands are divided into two segments [3]. Compared to the well-known Schoolbook method, the KOA saves multiplications of the partial products at the cost of extra additions. Further work of hardware and software implementations of Karatsuba-Ofman multipliers in literature, was done to improve the KOA and to find bounds of the complexity. Several works detailed information on the usage of KOA in order to multiply with the least cost are provided [2, 22]. Multiplying long numbers ($n \geq 128$ -bit) using Karatsuba-Ofman algorithm is fast but the algorithm is highly recursive. Our work is related to Karatsuba-Ofman multiplier for large numbers. In this paper, we proposed and developed different Karatsuba-Ofman multiplier designs in $GF(2^n)$, intended to perform the design of the cryptographic protocols in embedded system such as smart card and mobile phone. Our design constraints are: the latency, the energy consumption and the area occupation.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: The illustration of the efficiency of the multiplication arithmetic operator throughout the applications of cryptographic protocols for embedded systems is described in Section 2. Section 3 describes the Recursive Karatsuba-Ofman multiplication. In Section 4, we present new designs of adapted KOA, so that it can be implemented efficiently. Many approaches to Sequential and Parallel Recursive Karatsuba-Ofman Multipliers (RKM) to optimize the designs are developed in this section. Experimental results of FPGA implementation (area, latency, power) are presented in Section 5. Mathematical models (Area (n), Delay (n)) of our proposed Sequential/Parallel designs are also elaborated in Section 6. Section 7 concludes the paper.

II. EFFICIENT CRYPTOGRAPHIC PROTOCOLS FOR EMBEDDED SYSTEM

Embedded systems (such as : smart cards, mobile phones, Personal Digital Assistants, etc.), which ubiquitously are used

to capture, store, manipulate, and access data of a sensitive nature, pose several unique and interesting security challenges [12]. Therefore, providing security and trust in embedded systems raises important technological challenges. The cryptographic primitives and security protocols are hard to realize in embedded systems.

Embedded systems are extremely resource constrained devices in terms of computing and communication capabilities, energy, power, chip and memory area, etc. Moreover, they generally have to work in harsh, uncontrolled, and even hostile surrounding conditions. The security is not only the addition of features, such as specific cryptographic algorithms and security protocols, to the system but also the elaboration of novel design principles, methods, algorithms, designs and techniques in order to efficiently and securely realize cryptographic primitives and security protocols for embedded systems [23], which are the building blocks for security, privacy, and trust. The implementation of cryptographic systems presents several requirements and challenges. First, the performance of the algorithms is often crucial. One needs encryption algorithms to run at the transmission rates of the communication links. Slow running cryptographic algorithms translate into consumer dissatisfaction and inconvenience. On the other hand, fast running encryption might mean high product costs since traditionally, higher speeds were achieved through custom hardware devices. Recently, ECCs are especially suited to smart cards because of the limited memory and computational power available on these devices. Another benefit of ECCs is that they can use a much shorter key length than other public key cryptosystems such as RSA to provide an equivalent level of security [5, 17]. For ECC systems, the most important operation is the scalar multiplication which is based on the finite field multiplication. For large integer, the efficiency of multiplication dominates the overall performance of ECC implementation [9, 10]. It was shown that as much as 85% of execution time is spent on multiplication for a typical point multiplication in ECC. (see figure 1).

Fig. 1 Distribution of area occupation in ECC point multiplication arithmetic

Several techniques of multiplication were introduced in literature. The KOA is recommended for many cryptosystems. Therefore, the performance is primarily determined by the efficient implementation of the arithmetic multiplication. In this context, new designs of Karatsuba-Ofman multiplication are necessary to achieve the following two goals: one goal is to design a high speed multiplier, the second goal is to reduce

the area and the power consumption for large numbers ($n \geq 64$ -bit) on embedded processors and constrained platforms.

Hence, in order to improve time, area and power requirements of the ECC (on $GF(2^n)$ with $n \geq 163$ -bit), it is essential to have a variety of Karatsuba-Ofman multiplication designs with consideration to trade-offs between the application and platform requirements.

III. RECURSIVE KARATSUBA-OFMAN MULTIPLICATION (RKM)

In this section, we introduce the fundamental KOA which can successfully be applied to polynomial multiplication. The fundamental Karatsuba-Ofman multiplication for polynomial in $GF(2^n)$ is a recursive divide-and-conquer technique. It is considered as one of the fastest way to multiply long numbers [11]. For polynomial multiplication with original Karatsuba method both operands have to be divided into two equal parts. If the length of operands is odd, they have to be padded with leading '0' [4]. Therefore, the KOA becomes recursive. A straightforward application of the KOA requires $\log_2(n)$ iteration steps for polynomials of degree $(n-1)$. Let $A = (a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{n-1})$ and $B = (b_0, b_1, \dots, b_{n-1})$, the binary representation of two long integers. The operands A and B can be decomposed into two equal-size parts A_1A_0 and B_1B_0 respectively, which represent the $n/2$ higher and lower order bits of A and B. We can split them into two parts as follows:

$$A(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} a_i x^i = \sum_{i=0}^{\frac{n}{2}-1} a_i x^i + \sum_{i=\frac{n}{2}}^{n-1} a_i x^i$$

$$= x^{\frac{n}{2}} \sum_{i=0}^{\frac{n}{2}-1} a_i x^i + \sum_{i=0}^{\frac{n}{2}-1} a_i x^i = x^{\frac{n}{2}} A_1 + A_0 \quad (1)$$

$$B(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} b_i x^i = \sum_{i=0}^{\frac{n}{2}-1} b_i x^i + \sum_{i=\frac{n}{2}}^{n-1} b_i x^i$$

$$= x^{\frac{n}{2}} \sum_{i=0}^{\frac{n}{2}-1} b_i x^i + \sum_{i=0}^{\frac{n}{2}-1} b_i x^i = x^{\frac{n}{2}} B_1 + B_0 \quad (2)$$

So the product $P(x) = A(x) \cdot B(x)$ can be computed as follows:

$$A(x)B(x) = A_0 B_0 + A_1 B_1 x^n + (A_1 B_0 + A_0 B_1) x^{n/2} \quad (3)$$

Equation 3 needs four $(n/2)$ -bits multiplications to compute the product $P(x)$. To improve the computation of $P(x)$, Equation 3 can be modified to Equation 5 as follows:

$$A_1 B_0 + A_0 B_1 = (A_1 + A_0)(B_1 + B_0) - A_1 B_1 - A_0 B_0$$

$$A(x)B(x) = A_0 B_0 + A_1 B_1 x^n + (A_0 B_0 + A_1 B_1 + (A_1 + A_0)(B_1 + B_0)) x^{n/2} \quad (5)$$

The result is:

$$A(x)B(x) = C_0 + C_1 x^n \quad (6)$$

Field multiplication can be performed into two steps. Firstly, we perform an ordinary polynomial multiplication of

two field elements as shown in Equation 5. Secondly, a reduction operation with an irreducible polynomial is needed to be performed in order to obtain the $(n - 1)$ degree polynomial. It is noticed that once the irreducible polynomial $F(x) = x^n + x^k + 1$ has been selected, the reduction step can be accomplished by using XOR gates only [3]. However, we want to focus on an efficient method based on KOA to calculate the polynomial multiplication. Figure 2 shows the procedure of KOA where A and B are two n -bit length polynomials.

Fig. 2 Karatsuba-Ofman's multiplication

The multiplication over $GF(2^n)$ is computed by a single AND operation. After completion of these polynomial multiplications, the final value of the lower half of C_0 as well as the upper half of C_1 are determined. The KOA can be applied recursively to the three polynomial multiplications. Hence, we can postpone the computations of the polynomial products A_0B_0 , A_1B_1 and $(A_1+A_0)(B_1+B_0)$; and instead we can split again each one of these three factors into three polynomial products. By applying recursively this strategy, each polynomial multiplication is transformed into three polynomial multiplications with their degrees reduced to about half of its previous value [7]. This leads immediately to a recursive construction process of Karatsuba-Ofman Multiplication (RKM), which builds Combinational Karatsuba Multiplier (CKMs) of width $n = 2^i$ for arbitrary $i \in \mathbb{N}$ [13, 14]. (see figure 3).

(a) CKM1 : 1 bit (b) CKM2 : 2 bits (c) CKM4 : 4bits
 Fig. 3 Recursive Karatsuba-Ofman multiplication (RKM)

As can be concluded, parallel multipliers perform partial products in minimum clock cycle but require more area to be implemented. The area occupation metric becomes more and more important for $n \geq 64$ -bit. Therefore, we required new RKM designs to adjust their performances: delays; and especially area occupation.

IV. PROPOSED RKM DESIGNS

Multiplication can be implemented either in serially or parallel. In one side, serial multipliers require small area, less complex structure and high latency. In the other side, parallel multipliers perform the total operation in a minimum clock cycle but require more space to be implemented. When the operands are long ($n \geq 64$ -bit), the performances of the algorithm especially the area occupation, is deteriorated as will be shown in section 5.1. This problem is not noticed for little numbers ($n < 64$ -bit). Hence, to ameliorate the performances of RKM with $n \geq 64$ -bit, we proposed new hybrid RKM designs that can be adapted to various performances as known: delay, area and power constraints for large finite field's elements.

Fig. 4 Design of Recursive 128-bit Karatsuba-Ofman's multiplication (RKM)

A block diagram of 128-bit RKM's design is developed as shown in Figure 4.

The design includes the following units:

- Architecture Unit (AU): Constituted by 64-bit, 32-bit

and 16-bit RKM multipliers. It takes care of reading operands from a port operand memory.

- Memory (RAM): is used to load initial operands.
- Arithmetic Control Unit (ACU): generates control

signal for all other units and the memory.

- Finite State Machine (FSM): determinates when enable, reset the multiplication process, accept input data and register output results in the memory. It decided when the result obtained is to be used or ignored.

these designs are based on Parallel and Sequential applications of RKM. The major purpose of these approaches is to obtain a reduced area consumption and power of the hardware designs. The second purpose is to keep the high speed performance of RKM hardware implementations.

In order to optimize this design, we have developed and tested five new 64-bit RKM designs as shown in Figure 5 and 6. All

Fig. 5 A proposed 64-bit RKMj designs using Three parallel 32-bit RKM with (a) Three parallel 16-bit RKM; (b) Two parallel and one sequential 16-bit RKM; (c) Three sequential 16-bit RKM

Fig. 6 A proposed 64-bit RKMj designs using Two parallel, one sequential 32-bit RKM with (a) Three parallel 16-bit RKM; (b) Two parallel and one sequential 16-bit RKM

The proposed Parallel and Sequential 64-bit RKMj progress cycles are shown in Table 1. For two proposed designs, multitasks sequences functions are detailed. Table 1 shows all

steps describing the Architecture Units activation and deactivation. For example, to perform 64-bit RKM using RKM1, three 16-bit multipliers are performed in parallel; all

16-bit AUs are active "ON". Therefore, the three 32-bit RKM's required are consequently active "ON". However, when applying RKM2, the two 16-bit AUs are done in parallel (active: "ON"). Next sub-step, 16-bit AU is performed

sequentially; the other unit is deactivated ("OFF") as shown in Table 2. Consequently, the three 32-bit RKM's are activated in parallel.

TABLE I
 CYCLE PROGRESS OF 64-BIT RKM1 DESIGN

64-bit RKM1	32-bit RKM			32-bit RKM			32-bit RKM			
	16-bit RKM									
Step1	1.1	ON	ON							
Step2		ON			ON			ON		
Result Ready										

TABLE II
 CYCLE PROGRESS OF 64-BIT RKM2 DESIGN

64-bit RKM2	32-bit RKM		32-bit RKM		32-bit RKM	
	16-bit RKM					
Step 1	1.1	ON	ON	ON	ON	ON
	1.2	ON	OFF	ON	OFF	ON
Step 2	ON		ON		ON	
Result Ready						

In the following, we note A_{ij} with i the number of 128-bit RKM's ($i \in [1, 3]$) and j the number of 64-bit RKM applied ($j \in [1, 5]$).

So, we have fourteen 128-bit RKM designs. The detailed proposed designs are shown in Figure 7.

Fig.7 Three proposed 128-bit RKM designs

Table 3 presents the cycle number of 128-bit RKM designs.

TABLE III
 CYCLE REQUIREMENTS OF 128-BIT RKM'S DESIGN

Number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
Design	A_{11}	A_{21}	A_{31}	A_{12}	A_{32}	A_{14}	A_{24}	A_{34}	A_{15}	A_{25}	A_{35}	A_{13}	A_{23}	A_{33}
Cycle number	13	28	42	25	78	26	52	78	48	96	144	34	70	105

As can be seen, the design A_{11} needs 13 cycles to perform a full 128-bit multiplication. So, it's the fastest proposed design.

V. IMPLEMENTATION AND COMPARISONS RESULTS

In this section we present the results obtained from fourteen proposed 128-bit RKM's designs and we give some recommendations for RKM designs with focus on the cell-based design techniques. The different proposed designs are implemented in the Very High Speed Integrated Circuit Description Language -VHDL by using the Model

Technology's ModelSim Simulator. The VHDL codes of the different design are synthesized placed and routed using three target devices: Xilinx Virtex II 2v2000ff896-6, Xilinx Virtex E XCV2000Efg860-6 and Spartan 3s2000fg900-5 FPGAs. The designs were simulated for verification of the correct functionality.

According to the required performances design, performance metrics such as area occupation (slices), speed (ns) and power consumption (mW) are used. As can be seen, the 32-bit RKM design as know A_1 (three 16-bit RKM are

applied in parallel) is four time faster (154,163 ns) than the 32-bit RKM design as know A2 (three 16-bit RKM are applied sequentially) on two platforms. As concluded, when applying (A2), we obtain a profit of (26%) in speed with a little waste in area occupation by only (3%). Furthermore, the design (A1) takes (5 %) of the total number of CLB slices available in the same platform. Table 4 presents detailed results for 32 bit-RKM design. Still, the latency is the main metric of RKM algorithm when $n \leq 32$ -bit.

TABLE IV
 DELAY AND AREA PERFORMANCES OF 32-BIT A1 AND A2 DESIGNS ON TWO PLATFORMS

Designs		A1 (Parallel)	A2 (Sequential)
Delay (ns)	Spartan 3	40,7	154,163
	Virtex 2	24,31	113,264
Area (Slices%)	Spartan 3	5 %	2 %
	Virtex 2	6 %	4 %

A. 64-bit RKMj Implementation Results

The implementation results of the five 64-bit RKMj designs developed in the previous section are shown in Figure 8.

(a) Delay (ns)

(b) Area occupation (Slices)

(c) Power consumption (mW)

Fig. 8 Sensitivity tests: (a) Delay (ns); (b) Area occupation (Slices); (c) Power consumption (mW) for five 64-bit RKMj's designs on Virtex 2

As can be noticed the 64-bit RKM1 design presents the best results in speed (30, 88 ns), however the area occupation is about 3263 slices and the power consumption 83,05mW. We can divide the five proposed 64-bit RKMj design in three groups: the high latency group (RKM1) and the low area occupation group (RKM5). The third group is composed by medium latency and medium occupation (RKMj with $j \in [2, 4]$). The 64-bit RKM3 design can be adopted as the optimal solution. The important point is to conserve the speed of the RKM, which is much more important than the waste in the area occupation. In the subsection below, we present the efficiency of the 128-bit RKM based on 64-bit RKMj designs.

B. 128-bit RKMij Implementation Results

Figure 9, shows the computation time (ns), area occupation (slices) and power consumption (mW) required by our proposed 128-bit RKM designs.

(a) Delay (ns)

(b) Area occupation (Slices)

(c) Power consumption (mW)

Fig. 9 Sensitivity tests: (a) Delay (ns); (b) Area occupation (Slices); (c) Power consumption (mW) for fourteen 128-bit RKMij's designs on Spartan 3, Virtex 2 and Virtex E

From figure 9.a, we remark that each design have a different computing time on three FPGAs devices. However, the design number 1 (A11) provides the least computing time to perform a 128-bit multiplication in all platforms. In figure

9.b, area performances are given in terms of total numbers of slices necessary for the implementation. The design (A11) has the worst area occupation on the three platforms. The design number 14 (A33) introduces the best area performances. As can be noticed, the proposed design number 14 (A33) requires the least power consumption on all targeted devices compared to the other proposed designs.

We conclude from figure 9.c, that independently of targeted FPGA devices, the 128-bit RKM's designs (A11) and (A33) can be adapted respectively to obtain a minimum delay and least area occupation. The different RKM's designs and circuits have to be adapted in order to take full advantage of the corresponding logic block resources of FPGAs. The choice of the adequate RKM design depends on the platform targeted and the goal aimed application.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 10 Delay, Area and Power criteria for fourteen 128-bit RKMij's designs on: (a) Spartan 3; (b) Virtex 2 (c); Virtex E

These figures can be adapted for user as a reference to choose the ideal RKM's design for a targeted FPGA platform. A study is also made on the adapted FPGA for all proposed RKM's designs in order to give to the designers the flexibility to make trade-offs between speed, area and power criteria. So to implement an RKM in a constrained platform, one need to consider trade-offs between these parameters and the user can get all advantages of his FPGA as depicted in Figure 10.

C. Comparisons results

Table 5 shows the performance results obtained by the Xilinx project synthesizer of our proposed RKM designs. A comparison performance result for the hardware implementations against each other is not straight forward. This is because, in literature large numbers (for $n \geq 128$ -bit) karatsuba multiplication are not treated. Furthermore, different proposed multiplier designs performances (delay (ns) and area occupation (Slices)) deduced from this study are compared with our previous work on multipliers as know booth and hybrid multiplier with 128-bit length [6]. Furthermore, Table 5 compares our designs with other works recently reported in literature [19] in terms of 240-bit karatsuba multipliers, using the Virtex II reconfigurable hardware platform.

TABLE V
 COMPARISON RESULTS OF MULTIPLIER DESIGNS ON VIRTEX-II OVER GF (2^{128}) AND GF (2^{240})

Ref.	Design	Delay (us)	Area (Slices)
Our previous work	Booth	2,183	4%
[6] GF(2^{128})	Hybrid multiplier	0,280	92%
[19] GF(2^{240})	Hybrid karatsuba	0,378	14%
	classical karatsuba	0,523	15%
This work GF(2^{128})	A31	0,153	37%
	A32	0,205	30%
	A23	0,250	39%
This work GF(2^{240})	A33	0,378	23%
	RKM	0.29	45%

In order to have a fair evaluation, we choose the (A31), (A32), (A23) and (A33) RKM designs because of optimal performances. We can see from Table 5 that the (A31) design is able to operate at a delay of 153, 93 ns, which is 14,267-times faster than the booth method. However, it occupied (33%) slices besides. Compared to hybrid multiplier, the (A23) design runs approximately at the same delay. In other side, it consumes (53%) slices less of the total platform area. The focus of [19] was to implement karatsuba in classical and hybrid karatsuba method for 240-bit length using the Virtex II as a target. We notice that our proposed RKM multiplier occupied more area occupation (+3332 and +3225 slices) compared to the hybrid and classical karatsuba methods developed in [19]. In the other side, our proposed RKM design is respectively 0.09us and 0.233us faster.

VI. RKM DESIGNS MODELING

The objective of this section is to present mathematical models (Area (n), Delay (n)) of the proposed 128-bit RKM designs. They enabled us to establish the basis of a mathematical formalism of the RKM designs.

These models are available to designers before hardware and software embedded system implementation. So, a clear idea is available for FPGA designers about the delay and the area occupation of the RKM multiplier for different bit rang (n=64, 128,256...).

Mathematical performances models of all proposed designs are elaborated on two platforms. In the following, we

presented mathematical modeling of two designs as know (A11) and (A33) ones.

Figure 11 shows that the two Area variation's curves of RKM designs have approximately a polynomial pace. However, in this figure they have no ideal pace because of peaks. To perform a polynomial fit on the active data plot, a Polynomial Fit Analysis is needed. In this operation, a number of points are drawn in the fit curve. The fit equation model of the Kth order is stated:

$$Y = A + B_1X + B_2X^2 + B_3X^3 + \dots + B_KX^K \quad (7)$$

With: A and Bi are the parameters.

Fig. 11 Mathematical model (Area (n)) of RKM multiplier based on:(a) A₁₁ design; (b) A₃₃ design

TABLE VI
 AREA (N) MODEL PARAMETERS OF RKM A11 AND A33 DSIGNS

Parameters		Mode Equation
For RKM-A11 architecture	Spartan 3	$A + B_1 n + B_2 n^2 + B_3 n^3$ $B_1 \in [16.84, 20.78], B_2 \in [0.53, 0.57],$ $B_3 \in [-6.49 E-4, -5.29 E-4]$
	Virtex 2	$A + B_1 n + B_2 n^2 + B_3 n^3$ $B_1 \in [16.88, 20.83], B_2 \in [0.53, 0.57],$ $B_3 \in [-6.39 E-4, -5.19 E-4]$
For RKM-A33 architecture	Spartan 3	$A + B_1 n + B_2 n^2$ $B_1 \in [6.43, 18.57], B_2 \in [0.06, 0.09]$
	Virtex 2	$A + B_1 n + B_2 n^2$ $B_1 \in [6.79, 18.63], B_2 \in [0.05, 0.09]$

We conclude that the Area (n) occupation of RKM multiplier bases on (A11) and (A33) designs are presented in Section 3 has respectively a third and second polynomial order. The model's parameters of the Area (n) are illustrated in Table 6.

From Figure 12, we conclude that Delay (n) performance of RKM multiplier bases on (A11) and (A33) designs has respectively a second and first exponential order. The exponential fitting equation is as follows:

$$y = y_0 + A_1 e^{-x/t_1} + A_2 e^{-x/t_2} \quad (8)$$

With: y_0 the offset; A_1 and A_2 the amplitude; t_1 and t_2 decay constant

The model's parameters are illustrated in Table 7.

Fig. 12 Mathematical model (Delay (n)) of RKM multiplier based on: (a) A11 design; (b) A33 design

TABLE VII
 DELAY (N) MODEL PARAMETERS OF RKM A11 AND A33 DESIGNS

Parameters		Mode Equation
RKM- A11 design	Spartan 3	$y_0 + A_1 \exp(-n/t_1) + A_2 \exp(-n/t_2)$ $A_1 \in [-43.4, -41.4], t_1 \in [122.6, 150.6]$ $A_2 \in [-35, -32.8], t_2 \in [9.8, 11.4]$
	Virtex 2	$y_0 + A_1 \exp(-n/t_1) + A_2 \exp(-n/t_2)$ $A_1 \in [-29.5, -27.7], t_1 \in [56, 77.6]$ $A_2 \in [18, 19], t_2 \in [0.53, 0.57]$
RKM- A33 design	Spartan 3	$y_0 + A_1 \exp(-n/t_1)$ $A_1 \in [-884, -564], t_1 \in [57.9, 196.5]$
	Virtex 2	$y_0 + A_1 \exp(-n/t_1)$ $A_1 \in [-64.4, 399.4], t_1 \in [-198.7, -21.3]$

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we elaborated and presented RKM multiplier designs for large numbers ($n \geq 64$ bit). We explained that there are various ways to implement RKM that depends on the targeted platform and the goal aimed applications. For each method, we detailed the hardware design and the performance metrics (delay, area).

Furthermore, mathematical performance models, as know

delay (n) and area (n) of all proposed RKM designs are elaborated and evaluated. A clear idea is available for FPGA's designer about area occupation and delay of RKM's multiplier for different bit range ($n \geq 64$ bit). This feature is advantageous to have suitable trade-offs between Area and Speed for implementing cryptographic schemes in embedded systems. The goal of our RKM design is crucial for achieving high performance and energy efficient cryptographic protocols. However, the effectiveness of based design depends on the adopted design approaches.

Future works will focus on improving and applying our RKM designs to prevent advanced attacks (Side Channel Attacks such as: SPA, DPA).

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